

Empirical Research, Pitfalls, and Remedies: A Critical Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Neophytes in research are stuck with the problem according to which they believe that the way they learned to write essays in high school and undergraduate humanities classes is the only way by which to pen an article. Empirical research is basic to data-driven and evidence-based production of knowledge in the natural sciences, social sciences, education, and public policy. Though countless research methodology textbooks are available, researchers still commit errors in conceptualization, methodology, analysis, and research ethics. These mistakes undermine the quality and integrity of their work. The general purpose of this paper is to examine the key elements of empirical research, common pitfalls in research writing, and propose practical remedies based on well-established methodology scholarship. The specific objectives of this study are to provide the reasons for which there is a prescribed structure in qualitative social science research papers and to enumerate the elements thereof, 2) spot common errors, and 3) suggest ways in which these blunders can be rectified. I employed a qualitative analytical review of top research methodology books and peer-reviewed scholarly articles. This paper synthesized basic principles in qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods research. RQ1: It provided the key elements of a research manuscript. RQ2: It identified the most common errors are vague problem statements, weak literature synthesis, methodological non-alignment, sampling bias, shallow analysis, plagiarism, and unwarranted conclusion. The article ends by explaining that facts and figures alone are necessary but insufficient, as researchers must provide recommendations for policy, practice, and further research. Research congruence is key to empirical rigor. In short, the research problems, research objectives, research questions, methodology, data collection, data collection, data analysis, findings, discussion, and conclusion must match and cohere. Ethical reflexivity, methodology alignment, critical analytical writing, and transparency in reporting are crucial for scholarly credibility. This article contributes to a bird's-eye view to improve the quality of empirical research in academia and policy circles.

Keywords: Empirical Research, Literature Review, Research, Methodology, Natural and Social Sciences

Introduction

Overview

This article is a systematic examination of empirical research architecture, methodological pitfalls, and corrective strategies. It focuses on internal coherence, accuracy, and reproducibility across manuscript components.

Research Area

This paper lays in the field of empirical research methodology. The topic is manuscript construction. It deals with research concurrence, identification of methodological errors, and implementation of remedies.

Background of the Problem

Empirical research is the foundation of data-driven and evidence-based knowledge production. This applies to the natural sciences, social sciences, economics, business, management, education, public policy, and peace research. Empirical research systematically investigates natural, biological, and social realities using observable, measurable or interpretable evidence (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Problem Statement

Real-world problem involves the proliferation of empirically weak studies affecting the trustworthiness of knowledge and policy decisions. Publication of research with low internal consistency, sampling bias, and analytical errors abound. Methodological problem relates to fragmentation of methodological knowledge across textbooks and guidelines. Absence of integrated frameworks linking research elements, pitfalls, and remedies leaves a void. Some research papers contain major weaknesses. They include vague research problems, artificial research gaps, weak literature reviews, methodological mismatch, invalid conclusions, plagiarism, and lack of critical analysis. These challenges reduce accuracy, credibility, trustworthiness, and practical usefulness.

Research Gaps

Empirically, Existing methodology textbooks are often technical-focused and fragmented. As a result, novice researchers have problems in conducting systematic research. Generally, heterogeneous quality of empirical studies characterizes the state of journals and disciplines. Inconsistent methodological rigor embodies volumes of publications. Persistent issues include weak design, invalid inferences, and limited reproducibility. Conceptually, many neophyte researchers memorize research sections mechanically without understanding their logical integration and analytic aims. Practically, beginner researchers struggle to align research questions, objectives, theories, methods, results or findings, discussion, and conclusion coherently.

Research Questions

RQ1: What are the major sections and elements of empirical research? RQ2: Why do common methodological problems occur in empirical research? RQ3: How can researchers improve rigor, accuracy, coherence, and critical analysis in empirical studies?

Significance

This paper helps researchers, students, and policy analysts improve research quality, critical thinking, and evidence-based inquiry.

Literature Review

Overview. This literature review critically synthesizes major methodology textbooks and frameworks. It highlights their contributions, limitations, and relevance to understanding empirical research structure, common pitfalls, and remedies. It emphasizes alignment among research sections, procedural rigor, reflexivity, and ethical practice. It directly supports the objective of this study to create a simplified yet academically rigorous framework. Due to page limits in author guidelines, the literature reviews are presented in two matrices. See the Tables below.

Table 1 Critical Review of Textbooks on Research Methodology

Textbooks	Contributions	Pitfalls	Remedies
<i>Research Design</i> (Creswell & Creswell, 2018)	Clear alignment among paradigm, research design, data collection, and analysis; introduces mixed methods integration	Can encourage robotic usage of templates; limited attention to power, reflexivity, and critical thinking	Stress reflective application, contextual adaptation, and explicit alignment of manuscript sections
<i>Research Methods for Business</i> (Saunders et al., 2023)	Practical procedural guidelines; Clarifies decision-making from philosophy to data analysis	Oversimplifies philosophical debates; business examples may reduce applicability to other contexts	Adapts layers critically to social science and other contexts; incorporate explicit methodological reasoning
<i>Case Study Research</i> (Yin, 2018)	Calls for rigorous case study design, triangulation, and evidence chain	Post-positivist orientation may neglect interpretive depth and reflexivity	Integrate interpretive reflexive strategies along with protocol-based rigor
<i>Constructing Grounded Theory</i> (Charmaz, 2006)	Supports co-construction of meaning; stresses reflexivity	Risk of relativism or inconsistent analytical boundaries, if poorly applied	Combine systematic coding with transparent analytic decisions and alignment with RQs
<i>The Craft of Research</i> (Booth et al., 2016)	Clarifies argument construction, use of evidence, and scholarly communication	Focuses on writing logic over structural, ethical, or power-based critique	Pair argument construction with methodological rigor, ethnical reflection, and integration of manuscript sections

Table 2 Critical Review of Paradigms on Research Methodology

Paradigms (Ty, 2023a, 2025b)	Contributions	Pitfalls	Remedies
Positivism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Generalizable laws through hypothesis testing -Prediction, control -Surveys, experiments, statistics -Validity, reliability (Comte, 2023; Durkheim, 1915) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reductionism; ignores meaning and context -False objectivity; hidden research bias -Silent on power and justice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mixed methods -Statement on reflexivity -Embed context variables and equity indicators
Interpretivism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Rich contextualized understanding of lived experiences -Meaning making -Interviews, ethnography, hermeneutics (Geertz, 1973; Weber, 2019) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Limited or no generalizability -Subjectivity, non-replicability -Underplay power and structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Triangulation -Audit trails, inter-coder checks -Link micro-meanings to meso and macro structures
Critical Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Power, ideology, domination -emancipation, social justice -critique ideology -Participatory action research (Freire, 2005, 2014; Habermas et al., 2007; Horkheimer, 2002) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Normative bias, risk of advocacy over analysis -Overgeneralization of oppression frames -Access and feasibility constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Method pluralism with empirical rigor -Research participant co-design but keep analytic check -Specify mechanism and causal pathways
Transformative Paradigm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Structural economic and political change -Systemic inequities require systemic change -Structural analysis, movement-based inquiry (Burrell, 2016; Holst, 2002; Novelli et al., 2024; Ty, 2016a, 2016b, 2020b, 2023b) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Implementation gap: high resistance -Risk of polarization -May neglect incremental gains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Phased strategy: long, medium, and short terms -Networking, cooperation, collaboration, coalition, and alliance building -Combine small changes and structural overhaul

Summary of Literature Review

This critical literature review demonstrates that empirical research requires both technical rigor and critical reflexivity. Existing methodology textbooks and paradigms offer valuable foundations. But they differ in philosophical assumptions, analytical depth, and practical applicability. There this article adopts a pragmatic-critical analytic synthesis, integrating procedural rigor with contextual and reflexive analysis.

Gaps in the Literature

Weak literature reviews often summarize research without synthesizing theoretical debates, methodological strengths, contradictions, and research gaps (Hart, 2025). Research novices frequently fail to align conceptual frameworks with methodological choice (Maxwell, 2025). Despite extensive methodological literature, rarely do studies systematically integrate elements of empirical research, common pitfalls, structural causes, ethical implications, and practical remedies within one coherent framework (Ty, 2025a). This article addresses this research gap. See Figure below.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

The research design of this paper is a qualitative analytical synthesis of major methodology literature and empirical research principles. The research paradigm is pragmatic, critical-interpretive, explanatory, practical, and critical analytic. Collection of data is derived foundational social science methodology textbooks cited in this manuscript and additional methodology manuals (Ty, 2020a, 2024). Data analysis involved critical thematic synthesis of methodology literature through thematic coding, comparison, critical analytical interpretation, and synthesis. For accuracy, triangulation of key methodology sources, conceptual consistency, and logical coherence were ensured.

Findings

Due to page limits based on author guidelines, RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3 findings are presented in tabular format. See Table below.

Table 3 Alignment for Valid or Accurate, Reliable or Consistent, Ethical, and Impactful Research

RQ1		RQ2	RQ3	
Research Stage (Elements)	Core Elements (What)	Pitfalls (Why They Occur)	Remedies (How to Address)	Why It Matters (Evidence & Impact)
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Real-world problem -Theoretical or methodological program -Research gap -Significance and motivation -Research questions or hypotheses -Key terms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -No real-world problem -No scholarly gap -Gap not evidenced -Unclear importance -vague or not measurable research questions -Undefined terms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -State clear real-world issues -identify conceptual or methods gap -Show gap in literature -Explain why it matters -Formulate SMART RQs or hypotheses -Define all keywords 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clear and specific problems and RQs or hypotheses increase accuracy and research relevance (Creswell, 2014; Saunders et al., 2023)
Literature Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Knowledge landscape -Critical synthesis -Identify gaps -Conceptual or theoretical framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -incomplete, not most important, or outdated sources -descriptive, not analytical -gap not derived from synthesis -themes not connected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Comprehensive latest search -Compare, contrast, integrate -Derive gap logically -Build coherent framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Strong synthesis improves theoretical grounding and justification of the research (Bryman, 2016; Cooper, 2010)
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Research design -Unit of analysis -Sampling strategy -Data collection methods -Measurement and operationalization -Credibility or Validity -Dependability or Reliability -Data analysis technique -Data interpretation -Reflexivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Design-RQ mismatch -Ecological atomistic level of analysis fallacy -Sampling bias -Poor data quality -Invalid concepts -Inaccuracy and inconsistency -Wrongly mismatch qualitative and quantitative vocabulary -wrong assumptions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Research alignment -Clear definition of units -Justify sampling -Standardize procedures -Use validated instruments -Ensure credibility and dependability -Match analysis to data -Interpret within design limits -Disclose positionality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Rigorous execution -Appropriate, complete, reproducible, ethical, and transparent methods and tools provide methodological rigor which maximizes internal accuracy, consistency, and ethical integrity (Creswell, 2014; Lincoln & Guba,

RQ1		RQ2	RQ3	
Research Stage (Elements)	Core Elements (What)	Pitfalls (Why They Occur)	Remedies (How to Address)	Why It Matters (Evidence & Impact)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ethics (IRB, consent, confidentiality) -Transparent reporting -Reproducibility (data, code, index of item-objective congruence) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -overclaim or causal fallacy -Hidden researcher bias -Ethical violations -Non-transparent methods -Non-reproducible results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Obtain IRB and informed consent -Full methodological disclosure -Share data and code for verification and replicability -Vocabulary consistency 	1985; Shadish et al., 20)
Findings or Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Alignment with RQs or hypotheses -Data presentation -Analytical accuracy -Effect sizes and qualitative depth -Robustness and sensitivity checks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Findings or results do not answer RQs or hypotheses -Poor or unclear presentation -Misapplied statistics or models -No depth -No robustness check 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Map findings or results to each RQ or hypothesis -Clear tables, figures, and narratives -Use correct tests and models -Report effect sizes and themes -Conduct robustness and sensitivity tests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Honest reporting -Accurate findings or results strengthen conclusions and support reproducibility (Creswell, 2014; Shadish et al., 20)
Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Interpretation of findings or results -Link to literature -Theoretical implications -Practical or policy implications -Limitations of the study -Future research directions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Over-interpretation -No linkage to literature -No theoretical contribution -No practical implications -Ignored limitations -No suggestions for future research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Interpret with evidence -Compare with prior studies -Explain theoretical significance -Discuss real-world relevance -Acknowledge limitations -Suggest future research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Critical discussion improves external usefulness and contribution to knowledge (Bryman, 2016; Saunders et al., 2023)
Conclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Key findings or results summary -Contribution to knowledge -Contribution to practice and policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Summary and RQs not aligned -No knowledge contributions -No practical contributions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Summarize each RQ or hypothesis -Clearly stated contributions -Link to practice or policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Strong conclusions enhance impact, usability, and policy change (Cooper, 2010;

RQ1		RQ2	RQ3	
Research Stage (Elements)	Core Elements (What)	Pitfalls (Why They Occur)	Remedies (How to Address)	Why It Matters (Evidence & Impact)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Realistic Recommendations -No new theories and concepts here -Final implications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Unrealistic recommendations -Use new concepts or theories here -Unclear implications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Provide feasible recommendations -Do not introduce new concepts or theories -State clearly final implications 	Saunders et al., 2023)

Discussion

The findings confirm empirical research is not merely a technical procedure. Rather, it is a logically integrated and ethically grounded process. Strong empirical studies require coherence among all research sections. Research alignment is central. Misalignment causes problems: irrelevant findings or results, unsupported conclusion, methodological contradictions, and weak implications. One major problem is methodological reductionism and “methodolatry” or the blind worship of methodology where researchers mechanically follow templates only without understanding the philosophical and logical underpinnings. Yet, they do not understand the philosophical assumptions or contextual realities. This study contributes an integrated diagnostic framework connecting methodological rigor, ethics, and reflexivity. The analysis reveals that power relations shape empirical research. “Neutral and objective” research may unintentionally reproduce elite interests, colonial epistemologies, and structural inequalities. Poorly designed research may reinforce elite narratives, stereotypes, or conflict escalation. Thus, research design must coherently integrate philosophical assumptions, methods, and interpretation. Another issue involves the misuse of quantitative results. Statistical significance does not automatically imply social significance, ethical legitimacy, or causal certainty. Conversely, qualitative research is sometimes unfairly criticized as “subjective,” despite its strength in capturing lived experiences, context, identity, trauma, and meaning. Researcher self-reflexivity is vital. Researchers influence research through positionality, assumptions, values, and interpretation. Thus, reflexive awareness improves transparency and credibility. This paper is limited to the major social science methodology canons.

Conclusion

Summary

RQ1: Empirical rigor necessitates alignment across all components in the different stages of research. RQ2: Misalignment or non-concurrence results in invalid conclusions, wasted resources, and misleading implication. RQ3: Empirical research requires careful planning, rigorous execution, honest reporting, and external impact.

Recommendations

Researchers are recommended to strengthen their methodological literacy. Universities are enjoined to support faculty development in this regard. Further research can be conducted to explore decolonial research methodology.

Conclusion

Empirical research is not simply technical procedure. It is a rigorous, analytical, and ethical process. Weak research design, superficial analysis, methodological inconsistency, and unsupported claims undermine knowledge production and public trust. Transparent methodology, critical synthesis, reflexivity, as well as data-driven and evidence-based interpretation strengthen research credibility and social relevance.

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13th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress

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